

Silica gel supported sodium hydrogensulfate as a heterogenous catalyst for high yield synthesis of 2-arylbenzothiazoles

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Abstract : Silica gel supported sodium bisulfate catalyzes efficiently the synthesis of 2-arylbenzothiazoles by the condensation of 2-aminothiophenol and aromatic aldehyde in refluxing acetonitrile to afford the corresponding 2-arylbenzothiazoles.

Keywords : Heterogeneous catalyst, silica gel.

2-Arylbezothiazole nucleus constitutes the core unit of many therapeutic agents including antitumour drugs¹. Thus the synthesis of this heterocyclic system is of interest and a number of procedures have been reported²⁻⁴. However many of these procedures are associated with several problems such as expensive catalysts (Pd derivative)⁵, toxic, hazardous and carcinogenic organic solvents like nitrobenzene⁶, ionic liquids⁷, unsatisfactory yields and non recoverable catalyst. Therefore, this reaction continues to attract the attention of researchers for the discovery of milder, an inexpensive catalyst and efficient procedures for the synthesis of 2-arylbenzothiazoles.

Results and discussion

The use of solid supported reagents⁸ has received considerable importance in organic synthesis. In view of recent surge in the use of heterogeneous catalysts^{9,10}, we report a simple, convenient and efficient method for the preparation of 2-arylbezothiazole using a solid supported reagent, SiO₂-NaHSO₄, as an inexpensive and eco-friendly catalyst. This method not only affords the products in excellent yields but also avoids the problems associated with catalyst cost, handling, safety and pollution. We report here very simple synthesis of 2-arylbenzothiazoles by the condensation of 2-aminothiophenol and aromatic aldehydes in presence of heterogeneous catalysts (Scheme 1).

The reaction of 2-aminothiophenol (5 mmol) and benzaldehyde (5 mmol) in the presence of 5 mol% SiO₂-NaHSO₄ in refluxing acetonitrile (10 ml) resulted in the formation of 2-arylbezothiazole in 93% yield. Similarly,

Scheme 1

wide variety of aromatic aldehydes, heterocyclic aldehydes reacted well with 2-aminothiophenol under the reaction conditions to give the corresponding 2-arylbezothiazoles in excellent yields. The hetero cyclic aldehydes such as furfural, 2-thiophene, and 2-pyridine carboxaldehyde also furnish the corresponding benzothiazoles without any difficulty. All the products were characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, and mass spectral analysis and also by comparison with authentic samples. The reactions of various aldehydes with 2-aminothiophenol in the presence of silica gel supported sodium bisulfate be superior in terms of yields and reaction rates and the results are presented in the Table 1.

In conclusion, we have developed a simple, convenient and effective method for the synthesis of 2-arylbenzothiazoles by using NaHSO₄-SiO₂ under slightly acidic conditions. This method is applicable for a wide range of substrates. Present methodology offers very attractive features such as reduced reaction times, higher yields and economic viability of the catalyst, when compared with other catalysts, which will have wide scope in organic synthesis. To best of our knowledge this is the first report of the synthesis of 2-arylbenzothiazoles in the presence of NaHSO₄-SiO₂ catalyst.

Table 1. SiO₂-NaHSO₄ catalysed synthesis of 2-arylbenzothiazoles

Entry	Aldehyde	Product ^a	Reaction time (h)	Yield ^b (%)
a		3a	5.5	93
b		3b	6.0	88
c		3c	6.5	85
d		3d	6.5	85
e		3e	6.0	84
f		3f	6.0	80
g		3g	6.5	82
h		3h	6.0	80
i		3i	6.0	82
j		3j	6.0	80
k		3k	6.5	84
l		3l	6.5	82
m		3m	6.5	85
n		3n	5.0	85
o		3o	5.5	90
p		3p	6.0	85
q		3q	6.0	85

^aAll product were characterised by ¹H NMR and IR spectroscopic data and their m.p.s compared with literature m.p.s.

^bIsolated yields after column chromatography.

Experimental

General procedure : A mixture of 2-aminothiophenol (5 mmol), aromatic aldehyde (5 mmol) were dissolved in acetonitrile (10 mL) and stirred at reflux temperature. To this NaHSO₄-SiO₂ catalyst (5 mol%) was added and reaction mixture was stirred at reflux temperature for appropriate time (Table 1). After completion of the reaction as indicated by TLC, it was pored into ice cold water and

extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with sodium thiosulfate and water then dried and concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh) and eluted with ethyl acetate hexane (2.5 : 7.5) to afford 2-arylbenzothiazoles in 80–93% yields. The pure product was also obtained by recrystallisation of the crude solid from ethanol water. All the products were characterized by their melting points and spectroscopic data.

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